

Potentiometric study of the Complexes of Yttrium (III) with 4-(2-Pyridylazo) resorcinol, 1-(2'-Pyridylazo)-2-naphthol, Pyrocatechol violet, 2-(*p*-Sulphophenylazo)-1:8-dihydroxy naphthalene-3:6-disulphonate, and Gallion

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Potentiometric studies have been carried out on metal complexes of Yttrium (III) with 4-(2-Pyridylazo) resorcinol, 1-(2'-Pyridylazo)-2-naphthol, Pyrocatechol violet, 2-(*p*-Sulphophenylazo)-1:8-dihydroxynaphthalene-3:6-disulphonate, and Gallion. The Calvin-Bjerrum *pH*-titration technique, as used by Irving and Rossotti, has been applied to determine the stepwise protonation constants of the ligands and the formation constants of the complexes. The log *K* values have been computed by alternative methods. The values of overall changes in ΔG , ΔH , and ΔS accompanying complex formation have been evaluated at three different temperatures at an ionic strength of 0.1 *M* (NaClO₄).

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC study of the yttrium (III) complexes of 4-(2-Pyridylazo) resorcinol (PAR),

1-(2'-Pyridylazo)-2-naphthol (PAN), Pyrocatechol violet (PCV), and 2-(*p*-Sulphophenylazo)-1:8-dihydroxy naphthalene-3:6-disulphonate (SPADNS) has been reported earlier by different workers¹⁻⁶. However, the potentiometric study involving the stepwise formation of these complexes, has been reported for the first time in the present communication. Complexation reaction of yttrium(III) with Gallion (GAL) has also been reported for the first time in this paper. The "practical" proton-ligand stability constants of the ligands and the metal-ligand stability constants (stepwise) have been obtained by Bjerrum-Calvin titration technique^{7,8}, as used by Irving and Rossotti⁹. The overall free energy changes (ΔG), enthalpy changes (ΔH) and entropy changes (ΔS), associated with the equilibrium shown in equation (1) are also reported in this paper

Where A^{m-} represents the PAR, PAN, PCV SPADNS and GAL anions.

Experimental

A stock solution (0.02*M*) of YCl₃·6H₂O (E. Merck) was prepared in a calculated quantity of perchloric acid to prevent hydrolysis. The metal content was estimated by precipitating its oxalate and then dissolving it in H₂SO₄ and titrating the liberated oxalic acid against standardised permanganate solution. The stock solutions (6.0 × 10⁻³ *M*) of PAR (Reanal) and PAN (E. Merck) were prepared by dissolving the requisite quantities of the ligands in 50% dioxan-water media. Dioxan, which was used for preparing the solutions was purified before use¹⁰. The stock solutions (6.0 × 10⁻³ *M*) of PCV, (B. D. H.), SPADNS (Fluka) and GAL (Fluka) were prepared by dissolving the requisite quantities of the ligands in double distilled water. The solutions of these ligands were standardised potentiometrically.

Solutions of carbon dioxide free sodium hydroxide (E. Merck) and 0.1*M* perchloric acid (E. Merck) were standardised potentiometrically by usual procedures. A solution of sodium perchlorate was prepared by dissolving Anala R (Riedel) NaClO₄·H₂O in double distilled water.

A *pH*-meter (Beckman model H-2) with a glass-calomel electrode assembly was used to determine the change in hydrogen ion concentrations of the solutions, using KNO₃ salt bridge. A thermostat with resulting accuracy of ±0.2° was used.

Three mixtures were prepared containing acid, acid + ligand and acid + ligand + metal ion, such that the concentrations of the common ingredients were identical in different cases. Neutral sodium perchlorate solution was added to maintain the ionic strength ($\mu=0.1$). The ratio between the metal salt and the ligand was kept 1 : 5. The difference in the amount of sodium hydroxide utilised for the last two titrations is a measure of the extent of complexation.

To calculate the formation constants of ligandproton system, the values of \bar{n}_A at different *pH* values were calculated using the acid and ligand titration curves. The formation curves at different temperatures were obtained by plotting the graph between \bar{n}_A values and *pH*. The metal-ligand stability constants were obtained from the analysis of metal-ligand formation curves drawn between \bar{n} and *pL*. The values of the overall change in the free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) have been calculated at three different temperatures and ionic strength 0.1*M* (NaClO₄) with the help of the temperature co-efficient and Gibbs-Helmholtz equation¹¹.

Results and Discussion

From the titration curves it is observed that the metal-ligand curve is well separated from the ligand titration curve which proves that the liberation of

protons is due to chelation. Various computational methods^{1,2} viz. interpolation at half \bar{n} values, interpolation at various \bar{n} values, correction term method and least squares method, were applied to obtain the step-wise proton-ligand stability constants (error limits ± 0.02) and metal-ligand stability constants (error limits ± 0.03). The mean values at an ionic strength of $0.1M$ ($NaClO_4$) and at different temperatures have been summarised in Table 1 and Table 2.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF PROTONATION CONSTANTS ($\mu=0.1$)

Ligand	Constants	25°C	35°C	45°C
PAR	$\log K_1^H$	12.10	12.01	11.90
	$\log K_2^H$	5.65	5.55	5.46
	$\log \beta^H$	17.75	17.56	17.36
PAN	$\log K^H$	12.28	12.20	12.11
PCV	$\log K_1^H$	9.17	8.93	8.70
	$\log K_2^H$	5.44	5.34	5.25
	$\log \beta^H$	14.61	14.27	13.95
SPADNS	$\log K_1^H$	9.43	9.20	8.97
	$\log K_2^H$	8.58	8.32	8.08
	$\log \beta^H$	18.01	17.52	17.05
GAL	$\log K_1^H$	12.08	11.93	11.80
	$\log K_2^H$	5.14	5.03	4.90
	$\log \beta^H$	17.22	16.96	16.70

TABLE 2—METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS ($\mu=0.1$)

Complex	Constants	25°C	35°C	45°C
Y(III)-PAR (1:2)	$\log K_1$	12.58	12.50	12.43
	$\log K_2$	11.45	11.40	11.34
	$\log \beta$	24.03	23.90	23.77
Y(III)-PAN (1:2)	$\log K_1$	12.14	12.07	12.02
	$\log K_2$	10.45	10.36	10.25
	$\log \beta$	22.59	22.43	22.27
Y(III)-PCV (1:1)	$\log K$	6.81	6.42	6.05
Y(III)-SPADNS (1:1)	$\log K$	8.12	8.05	7.95
Y(III)-GAL (1:2)	$\log K_1$	11.45	11.40	11.34
	$\log K_2$	7.85	7.78	7.73
	$\log \beta$	19.30	19.18	19.07

Comparing the stability constants of the complexes of yttrium (III) with these organic dyes we observe that the order of stability of yttrium complexes is, PAR > PAN > GAL > SPADNS > PCV. The values of free energy changes (ΔG), enthalpy changes (ΔH) and entropy changes (ΔS) calculated at three different temperatures have been summarised in Table 3. Assuming that a major part of the errors in $\log K$ are systematic the precision of ΔH values is ± 0.5 Kcal/mol and the precision of ΔS values is ± 2.0 e.u.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF COMPLEXES ($\mu=0.1$)

Complex	Temp. °C	ΔG Kcal/mol	ΔH Kcal/mol	ΔS Cal/deg/mol
Y(III)-PAR	25	-32.76		
	35	-33.69	-5.9	+90
	45	-34.58		
Y(III)-PAN	25	-30.80		
	35	-31.61	-7.3	+79
	45	-32.41		
Y(III)-PCV	25	-9.28		
	35	-9.05	-11.4	-7
	45	-8.81		
Y(III)-SPADNS	25	-11.08		
	35	-11.34	-3.6	+25
	45	-11.57		
Y(III)-GAL	25	-26.32		
	35	-27.04	-5.3	+70
	45	-27.75		

Due to the lack of high precision in the values of ΔH and ΔS , a rigorous quantitative interpretation of the thermodynamic parameters cannot be tried. However, in all the complexes (except Y(III)-PCV) the values of enthalpy are negative and entropy values are positive, which shows that both the terms are favourable for the formation of complexes.

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